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Microplastics analysis: can we carry out a polymeric characterisation of atmospheric aerosol using direct inlet Py-GC/MS?

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Corresponding Author:	Elena Gregoris ITALY
First Author:	Elena Gregoris
Order of Authors:	Elena Gregoris Gaia Gallo Beatrice Rosso Rossano Piazza Fabiana Corami Andrea Gambaro
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Highlights

- Pyrolysis-GC/MS applied for the first time for microplastics in atmospheric aerosol
- Direct inlet Py-GC/MS used as an exploratory technique
- "Aerosol organic baseline" as an estimation of the interference of organic aerosol
- Plastics detected in atmospheric aerosol and commercial dust
- Further research is needed for a full polymeric profile of atmospheric aerosol

Question

Method

Findings

Fast explorative method for analysis of airborne microplastics?

Total suspended particulate

Direct inlet

Py-GC/MS

Detection of polymer tracers

✓ Polymers detected

✓ Good agreement with Micro-FTIR for pure particulate

Elena Gregoris: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualisation, Project administration. **Gaia Gallo:** Investigation, Validation. **Beatrice Rosso:** Investigation, Validation, Resources; **Rossano Piazza:** Resources; **Fabiana Corami:** Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing. **Andrea Gambaro:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Title

Microplastics analysis: can we carry out a polymeric characterisation of atmospheric aerosol using direct inlet Py-GC/MS?

Authors and affiliations

Elena Gregoris^{a,b}, Gaia Gallo^b, Beatrice Rosso^b, Rossano Piazza^b, Fabiana Corami^{a,b}, Andrea Gambaro^b

^aInstitute of Polar Sciences of the National Research Council of Italy (ISP-CNR), Via Torino 155, 30172 Venice (Italy)

^bDepartment of Environmental Science, Statistics and Informatics, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Via Torino 155, 30172 Venice (Italy)

Corresponding author

Elena Gregoris

elena.gregoris@cnr.it

Via Torino 155, 30172 Venice

+39 0412348637

Abstract

Microplastics are emerging pollutants of great concern since they are widely distributed in the environment. While the occurrence of microplastics was studied in marine and freshwaters, sediments, soil, and different classes of organisms, the atmosphere was somewhat understudied, although it can be the most significant transport pathway from mid to high latitudes. This work is one of the first studies testing the possible application of pyrolysis gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) for detecting polymers in atmospheric aerosol. It explored the possibility of a direct inlet analysis of sampling filters, proposing for the first time the calculation of an "aerosol organic baseline" for estimating the level of interferences to specific polymer tracers due to the organic matter content of atmospheric aerosol. The direct inlet analysis was tested for environmental samples and commercial dust, using the micro-FTIR analytical technique as a reference. Polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene were detected in atmospheric aerosol samples; PE, PP, and Nylon 6 (polyamide 6, PA6) were detected in the commercial dust. The first results obtained on the atmospheric aerosol allow for highlighting the technique's potential and drawing insights from the difficulties encountered. Results suggest that the direct analysis of the sampling filters can be employed as an exploratory technique due to its fast response, even if further research is needed to obtain a comprehensive polymeric characterisation of atmospheric aerosol.

Keywords

Microplastics; atmospheric aerosol; pyrolysis-GC/MS; polymer characterisation; matrix interference.

1 Introduction

Microplastics (MPs) are emerging pollutants of great concern widely distributed in the environment, which can be ingested by biota, and have also been reported in different environmental matrices of remote areas of Polar Regions [1]. The atmosphere is one of the main pathways for the transport of pollutants. The occurrence of MPs in the atmosphere was somewhat understudied; however, studies about this topic are rapidly increasing [2]. The first work giving evidence about the fallout of plastic fibres from the atmosphere to the ground is by Dris et al. [3]. Research conducted by Allen et al. [4] provided unequivocal evidence of

the direct atmospheric fallout of MPs in a remote area of the Pyrenees mountains. Analogously, the accumulation of MPs in national wilderness areas of the US and glaciers in the Tibetan Plateau was shown and related to the transport of particles by wind [5,6]. Atmospheric transport is now considered a significant pathway for microplastics to remote regions [7].

Currently, no standard methods exist for identifying and quantifying MPs in environmental samples [8]. Micro-FTIR and micro-Raman are the most used analytical techniques, often coupled with visual observations and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). In addition, pyrolysis gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) and other mass-based thermal desorption methods have been identified as promising techniques for MPs analysis in the environment; they are widely used for various environmental matrices, but they have rarely been employed in airborne MPs research yet [9,10,11]. In a Py-GC/MS, large high-molecular-weight molecules are thermally decomposed in an inert atmosphere to create a reproducible set of smaller low-molecular-weight products. Characteristic products are separated by gas chromatography and identified by mass spectrometry, giving information about the original polymer composition of the sample. Although mass-based analytical techniques cannot be considered complete methods for the analysis of MPs – since morphological analysis is not possible – it was demonstrated that such methods give more reliable results, in terms of polymer identification and mass quantification, compared to the others [12,13]. The direct introduction of the sample in the pyrolysis chamber of Py-GC/MS is possible, potentially avoiding the time-consuming sample preparation needed for applying the other techniques. Also, the identification of polymers by Py-GC/MS is not interfered with by degradation [13,14] or the presence of contaminants absorbed onto the particle surface [8].

The need to use multiple analytical techniques for MP analysis is commonly recognised in the literature [12,14], and Py-GC/MS could be helpful as a complementary technique to microscopy and/or spectroscopic methods. Due to the fast response, Py-GC/MS could also be applied as an exploratory technique, whose results could help in building an experimental design including other complete techniques for MP analysis. This work explores the applicability of Py-GC/MS as an exploratory and/or complementary technique for analysing MPs in the aerosol. It was conceived as an introductory work on the topic of the analysis of

microplastics in atmospheric aerosol, scarcely addressed in the literature. Several works mentioned the advantage of inserting the sample “as it is” in the pyrolyser because it permits significantly reduced analysis time and manipulation of the sample [15,16]. However, studies applying Py-GC/MS for MP quantification in environmental samples usually carry out time-consuming preparative steps, including extraction of particles and often a purification step for removing the organic interferences [10,17–21]; this practice seems to be necessary for obtaining reliable results. In this work, we explored possible applicability of Py-GC/MS for analysing aerosol filters without any preparative step, when quantification is not required, estimating the interference of organic aerosol in total suspended particulate (TSP) samples. Our aim is to provide a new simple and quick method to be exploited for assessing the presence of plastics in a sample, before the application of much more accurate and time-consuming techniques, dedicated to quantification. Direct inlet pyrolysis has already been applied to other fields, such as cultural heritage materials [22] and toxins analysis [23]. As to our knowledge, only the research teams of Fabbri [24] and Jones [11] used Py-GC/MS for analysis of the atmospheric aerosol as it is (specifically, PM₁₀) for qualitative purposes; while this is the first study that evaluates the possible interferences of the organic aerosol, with the specific purpose of assessing the applicability of this technique for the detection of MPs in the atmospheric aerosol. In our opinion, assessing the matrix interference is essential to understand if an organic matter removal step is necessary for an effective qualitative analysis of the urban atmospheric aerosol. Results were compared to those obtained using micro-FTIR as a reference technique.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Reagents and materials

Due to the lack of certified standards and certified reference materials, commercial polymers were employed as standards. Polyethylene (PE), polyethylenterephthalate (PET), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), polyamide 6 or Nylon 6 (PA6), polyamide 12 or Nylon 12 (PA12) were purchased from Goodfellow; polystyrene (PS) was provided by CDS Analytical; polypropylene (PP) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) were cut from plastic materials. Humic acid was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. House dust SRM2585 is a NIST (National Institute of Standards

and Technology) standard for organic contaminants in house dust; it is not certified for microplastics, but it was used for testing the applicability of the method.

Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂, 30%, Sigma-Aldrich), organic solvent-free and cold-pressed sunflower seeds oil (SSO, Crudolio), and high purity solvents (n-hexane, ethanol, and methanol, Sigma-Aldrich) were employed during pre-treatment procedures for MPs extraction. Ultrapure water (UW) is produced by a UW system (Elga Lab Water). Decontaminated quartz fibre filters (QFFs, porosity 1 µm, size 102 mm, SKC Inc.) were used to collect airborne particles. Aluminium oxide filters (0.2 µm, 47 mm diameter, ANODISC (Anopore Inorganic Membrane Whatman)) were purchased from Merck. More details are provided in the Supplementary Material (Table SM1).

2.2 Aerosol sampling

TSP samples were collected onto QFFs using a high-volume air sampler (AirFlowPUF, Analitica Strumenti; flow rate: 0.3 m³ min⁻¹). Before sampling, QFFs were furnace-treated at 400 °C for 4 h and individually wrapped in a double decontaminated aluminium foil. Sampling was carried out at the Scientific Campus of Ca' Foscari University (45°28'72"N, 12°15'35"E, Mestre-Venice, Italy, Figure SM1) in July 2021. Details about sampling dates and volume are reported in the Supplementary Material (Table SM2). Once collected, sample QFFs were divided in half to undergo two different procedures, and each piece was individually wrapped in a double decontaminated aluminium foil.

2.3 Identification of polymers via Py-GC/MS

Analyses were performed using a Pyroprobe 5150 filament pyrolyser (CDS Analytical) coupled with a high-resolution gas chromatograph HP 6890 - quadrupole mass spectrometer 5975N (Agilent Technologies). Standards were pyrolysed at various temperatures, in triplicate: 600°C, 700°C, 750°C and 800°C, for 15 s. The accessory program was constant, with a ventilation step for removing volatile and semi-volatile compounds (200°C, 3 min, raised to 280°C, 5 min; valve oven 250°C, transfer line 250°C). Standards were inserted in a pre-muffled (400°C, 4 h) open-ended quartz tube, between two quartz disks punched out from a pre-muffled QFF using a 2 mm puncher, provided by CDS Analytical. Standards were weighted using a Sartorius MSE3

balance (precision 0.001 mg) and directly inserted in the tube. The best pyrolysis temperature was evaluated by comparing the normalised area of indicator peaks of PE, PET and PA6. 20 disks were punched out from sample QFF to be inserted in the tube. After each analysis, the probe was cleaned at 1200°C for 10 s.

GC was equipped with an HP-5ms column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm, Agilent Technologies). Three temperature programs from the literature were tested (Table 1). A post-run of 10 minutes at the highest temperature of the program employed was added to all the programs.

The resolution was calculated using indicator peaks of PE (C₈-C₁₈), as reported in Hermabessiere et al. [25] and Okoffo et al. [19]:

$$\text{Resolution} = 2 \times (rt - rt_p) / (w - w_p)$$

where *rt* is the retention time of the n-alk-1-ene (hereinafter “alkene”), *rt_p* is the retention time of the n-α, ω-alkadiene (hereinafter “alkadiene”), *w* is the width of the alkene and *w_p* is the width of the alkadiene. The GC inlet temperature was 300°C; the split ratio was 1:20 for samples and 1:50 for standards to ensure a good transfer of the pyrolysate from the pyrolyser to the GC inlet port. The MS detector was used in scan mode from 45 to 400 *m/z*, with an ion source temperature of 230°C and a quadrupole temperature of 150°C.

Polymer identification was based on the presence of indicator compounds in the resulting pyrogram, taking into account the available literature about polymer characteristic pyrolytic products [12,13,20,21,25,28–30]. At present, a standard method for the identification of polymers through their pyrolytic products has not yet been defined. For some polymers, there is a shared indication in the literature about the specific tracer to be considered: caprolactam for PA6, tetrafluoroethylene for PTFE, vinyl benzoate for PET, styrene dimer (or the less abundant trimer) for PS, 2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene (or other high-molecular-weight oligomers) for PP. For PE, alkenes and alkadienes are used; for PVC, chlorobenzene has been identified as the univocal tracer, but sometimes the most interfered benzene and 1-methyl naphthalene are also used. PA12 is the less studied polymer in this list: it is known to produce alkenes, alkadienes and alkanenitriles up to C₁₁, when pyrolysed. In this work, we have monitored various tracers, including those generally considered univocal, some

controversial markers, and more generic ones (Table 2). For a further indication of the presence of PS or other styrene-based polymers, the Sty/Tol ratio > 1 was also considered [27,30].

Chromatographic peaks were identified by using the AMDIS (Automated Mass Spectral Deconvolution and Identification System) software. AMDIS is a sophisticated program developed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). The program scans all the ion chromatograms in a GC/MS data file and makes a deconvolution of peaks, based on the categorisation of ions with similar chromatographic behaviour (i.e., retention time and peak shape). Once their mass spectra have been extracted, single components are identified by comparison with a user target library. It is particularly useful in the case of complex samples with a strong background and coeluting peaks, for which the classical background correction is not applicable. Contrary to what happens with the classical identification methods, AMDIS permits taking into consideration the target retention time for identification, in addition to the mass spectra similarity, and automatise the identification process [32,33].

A target library was built for polymer identification, including the polymer markers selected before (Table 2), by loading mass spectra from in-house recorded chromatograms. The minimum match factor was set to 60%, as expected by default. The "use retention time" mode was applied, which gives a higher penalty to the identification match, more the retention time differs from that stored in the library. In addition, identified peaks with a retention time of more than one minute different than expected are manually excluded, or the peak shift is mentioned. Other parameters are reported in the Supplementary Material (Table SM3).

Since AMDIS is not a tool for quantifying of GC/MS data, the MSDChem GC/MS software was used whenever a peak integration was needed (i. e., LD calculation, repeatability assessment, etc.).

2.4 Pre-treatment procedure for micro-FTIR analysis: elutriation, oleo-extraction, and purification

The pre-treatment procedure (elutriation, oleo-extraction, and purification) for the identification of MPs in aerosol samples was developed in previous work [34]. Briefly, half QFF filter was sonicated for 10 seconds and then elutriated with 250 ml of UW and 5 ml of H₂O₂, stirring for 5 hours at 120 rpm on a multipurpose orbital shaker. Then, the aliquots from elutriation plus an increasing volume of UW was pouted to reach 300

ml in a decontaminated glass separating funnel, for the oleo-extraction procedure, according to Corami et al. [35].

For the oleo-extraction, 7 ml of SSO and 5 ml of H₂O₂ were added to a decontaminated separating funnel, which was hand-stirred by inversion to form an emulsion; the emulsion was then left to rest for 18 hours. Then, the water phase was carefully poured into a second decontaminated separating funnel, and the oleo-extraction was repeated by adding another 7 ml of SSO and letting it rest for 3 hours. The first oil extract was recovered with 20 ml of *n*-hexane and 20 ml of ethanol in a decontaminated Erlenmeyer flask, where the second oil extract was added after having discarded the aqueous phase.

The recovered oil extracts were filtered using a glass filtration system vacuum (Laboport) using an aluminium oxide filter. Before filtration, the filter was rinsed with a 50% (v/v) ethanol-methanol solution and a 70% (v/v) ethanol-methanol solution. Then, the oil extracts were flushed several times, alternating with *n*-hexane and 70% (v/v) ethanol-methanol solution. Purification was performed on the filter by flushing first a 70% (v/v) ethanol-methanol solution and then a 50% (v/v) ethanol-methanol solution to remove any residue and interferences from the filter surface. The filters were placed in decontaminated glass Petri dishes, left to dry at room temperature for 72 hours, then covered with aluminium foil and stored until the analysis time via Micro-FTIR.

2.5 Quantification and chemical identification via micro-FTIR

Micro-FTIR (Nicolet iN10 Thermofisher, Thermo Fisher Scientific), a Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectrometer coupled with a microscope, was employed for the identification of airborne MPs in atmospheric aerosol samples. The instrument was equipped with a Mercury Cadmium Telluride (MCT) detector cooled with liquid nitrogen. The PARTICLES WIZARD section of the Omnic™ Picta™ software was employed for the analysis, using the following parameters: transmittance mode, spectral range 4000–1200 cm⁻¹, 100-mm step size scanning (spatial resolution) at 100–100 mm aperture, and 64 co-added scans at the spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ [35]. The resulting spectra of the analysed particle were then compared with

several reference libraries previously selected. According to the similarity algorithm, a match percentage was obtained; the minimum percentage for the identification was 65%.

2.6 Quality assessment / Quality Control (QA/QC)

During sampling activities, all the operations were carried out to avoid plastic contamination. Before sampling, QFFs filters were furnace-treated at 400 °C for 4 h and individually wrapped in a double decontaminated aluminium foil. The sampler grid was washed with UW and ethanol, and decontaminated tweezers and aluminium foils were used for sample manipulation. During sampling, pre-treatment procedures, and analysis lab cotton coats and nitrile gloves were worn.

To assess the precision of the instrumental method, six runs with a known quantity of the selected standard polymers were carried out and the relative standard deviation (%) was calculated for characteristic peaks, representing the repeatability. The Instrumental Detection Limit (IDL) was calculated from the average of the blank values (two QFF disks in the sample tube, $n = 6$) of characteristic peaks, plus three standard deviations. The resulting value was converted into weight units, by comparison with the chromatographic peaks of the corresponding standard (average of 6 runs). A possible overlay of indicator peaks or interaction between polymers was checked by pyrolysing all standard polymers (about 100 µg each) at the same time. Also, it was verified whether the set pyrolysis time was sufficient to conduct a complete degradation of the sample, even changing the quantity of material inserted in the sample tube (from about 0.1 mg for standards to about 6-7 mg for samples). Preparation of samples for Py-GC/MS analysis was conducted under a laminar class hood (class II, standard EN 12469).

Pre-treatment filtration for micro-FTIR analysis and the decontamination procedures were performed in the cleanroom ISO 7, a suitable clean laboratory with controlled air circulation (plastic-free air filters) made of inox steel, where benches and fume hoods were decontaminated using a 50% (v/v) ethanol-methanol solution. All glassware (including filtration apparatus) and steel-ware are washed with a 1% solution of Citranox® and rinsed several times with ultrapure water with a 50% (v/v) solution of ethanol-methanol and pure ethanol and allowed to dry under a fume hood in the cleanroom. Field blanks, reagents and procedural

blanks were collected, pre-treated, and analysed as samples to verify contamination during sample handling and pre-treatment procedures.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Optimisation of the Py-GC/MS parameters

The pyrolysis temperature could influence the formation of the characteristic product. A recent work by Hermabessiere and colleagues [25] investigated the effect of temperature on PE using a micro-furnace pyrolyser, reporting an increase of the alkenes peak area from 500°C to 700°C and a decrease at 800°C. Based on this data, they selected 700°C as the best pyrolysis temperature and mentioned that it is the more used value for temperature in Py-GC/MS analysis. In this work, we expanded this assessment to alkadienes of PE, tracers of PET (benzene, acetophenone, vinyl benzoate, benzoic acid, and divinyl terephthalate) and PA6 (caprolactam) and evaluated the 750°C temperature too.

Results show a similar normalised area for alkene peaks at 600°C, 700°C and 750°C (Figure 1), with little differences among the congeners, whereas a decrease was observed at 800°C for all alkenes, according to what was found before [25]. Alkadienes show a little increase in the normalised area with rising pyrolysis temperature, reaching a maximum at 750°C and a decrease at 800°C. Low molecular weight alkadienes are of difficult identification at 600°C and are characterised by peak areas comparable or lower to that measured at 800°C. The alkadienes' behaviour as the temperature changes is of particular interest, since they are considered univocal tracers of PE, and suggests the use of 700°C or 750°C as the best pyrolysis temperature. The study of tracers of PET and PA6 did not provide other insights regarding the pyrolysis temperature choice. We selected 750°C as pyrolysis temperature, taking into consideration: i) the possible application of this method to a broad range of polymers, including those that pyrolyse at high temperature (i.e., PTFE, the temperature of complete pyrolysis: 629°C [36]); ii) in a filament pyrolyser the temperature is measured on

the wire and not inside the sample, thus the system should be set at a slightly higher temperature than the desired pyrolysis temperature (i.e., 50°C higher [15]).

The resolution was above 1.5 for all the selected characteristic peaks of PE, for all the methods, and in all repetitions; thus, all methods were considered suitable [19,25]. Resolution decreased moving from low to high carbon number due to the progressive gathering of peaks observed in the PE pyrogram, as carbon number increased. The highest resolution was observed for method C, coherent with the lower heating rate of the temperature ramp compared with the other methods; however, it adds up to an increase in the total analysis time (46 min). To find a compromise between the advantage of working with high resolution and with short runs, method B (32 min) was chosen, which was characterised by a resolution higher than 3 for all the alkene/alkadiene couples from C₈ to C₁₈ (Figure SM2).

Py-GC/MS is mainly used for the analysis of single particles [16,26]. In these conditions, the limit of detection (DL) is linked to the smallest particle that can be handled and physically transferred into the sample holder of the pyrolysis apparatus and was reported from 50 µm [37] to 0.1 µm [12]. Fischer and Scholz-Böttcher [20] reduced the LD to 3 ng using calibration solutions for soluble polymers, thus bypassing the problem of particle manipulation. Making a bulk analysis instead of selecting single particles permits to have no practical lower limit in particle size. In this case, the total polymer mass in a sample constrains the lower limit of the measurement instead of the particle size.

The instrumental detection limit (IDL), representing the minimum mass technically measured, was reported in Table 3. Blanks did not present any peaks identifiable as polymer tracer. Alkenes IDLs (0.01 to 0.05 µg) were lower than alkadienes IDLs (0.01-1.6 µg), according to the higher sensitivity of the instrument to alkenes than alkadienes. The same was observed for styrene (IDL 0.5 ng) and styrene dimer (1 µg). The IDLs for the other tracers were always lower than 0.04 µg, except for chlorobenzene (IDL 3.8 µg): this tracer is known to

be less sensitive than the other PVC pyrolysis products. In general, IDLs measured in this work are comparable or lower to that observed in the literature [27,38].

Identification of polymers was successful, with matches above 85% for almost all the tracers, in repeated tests (n=6, Table SM4): the only exceptions were 1,8-nonadiene (72-99%) and chlorobenzene (71-90%); so the method could be considered repeatable for qualitative analysis for PE, PP, PA12, PA6, PET, PP, PS, and PTFE, and less repeatable for PVC, if using chlorobenzene as the univocal tracer. Even if the aim of this work was not the quantification of polymers, the quantification of repeatability was also assessed (Table SM4) to fully characterise the applicability of Py-GC/MS for polymer analysis. RSD ranged from 6% to over 100%. High dispersion of data was observed for 1,7-octadiene (91%), divinyl terephthalate and acetophenone (over 100%), whereas the product leading to the most precise results was caprolactam (6%). Very little information about the precision of the mass spectrometer-based thermal systems is reported in the literature and it is referred to different configurations than filament Py-GC/MS. Microfurnace Py-GC/MS is the most used system, with an RSD ranging from 1 to 48% [15,25]. It seems that the poor reproducibility observed in this work could be due to the non-uniform heating of samples, typical of filament pyrolysers: temperature could be affected by the placement of samples into the sample tube, possible deformation of the coils and other heat-transfer variations [15]. However, this aspect did not affect the identification of polymers that were optimal also for tracers with lower quantitative reproducibility, whereas it suggests the appropriateness of conducting replicates for polymer detection using filament Py-GC/MS.

The necessity of replicates was also confirmed by the tests carried out with polymer standard mixtures. In single mixture pyrograms, not all inserted polymers could be detected, but the use of replicates allowed the detection of a greater number of polymers or to have a higher identification match. Among the studied polymers, only PVC was never detected in the mixture, probably due to the very low sensitivity of chlorobenzene. Details are reported in the Supplementary Material (Table SM5).

3.2 The Organic Aerosol Baseline (OAB)

The organic aerosol baseline (OAB) is a first attempt of estimation of the organic material contribution present in the atmospheric aerosol to the polymer tracer areas.. Organic aerosol is a complex mixture of various compounds, and its composition is still largely unknown. Only a few works assessed the interference of organic material to polymer indicator compounds [19,20] and they both use humic acid as a representative of organic matter. While being aware that it constitutes only a part of the organic material present in the aerosols, we also selected humic acid as the representative substance organic aerosol for this assessment. In the analysis of samples, only compounds with peak area above OAB were considered as detected.

First, knowing which polymers are involved in the interference by organic material is necessary. Some characteristic polymer peaks were detected among the pyrolytic products of humic acid (Figure SM3). Benzene, toluene, styrene, acetophenone, indene, and 1-methyl naphthalene are characteristic products of PS, PET, and PVC, as well as styrene-based rubbers [25,39]. However, they are rarely chosen as univocal tracers of polymers because they can be produced from several natural and artificial materials. In this work, they are used as support markers for polymer detection. Toluene is produced in much more abundant quantities than styrene; this allows the use of the Sty/Tol ratio for the identification of styrene-based polymers: a high Sty/Tol ratio necessary implies the production of styrene from polymers pyrolysis.

In addition, a series of alkanes and alkenes and some alkadienes were detected. Alkenes and alkanes are known to be formed by pyrolysis of natural material [19,20], and Dierkes and colleagues [18] also observed interference by 1,14-pentadecadiene. The use of alkenes for PE identification is still in debate in the scientific community. Some authors use a homologous series of PE triplets (n-alkanes, alkenes, and alkadienes) [21] or single alkadienes [27,42]; others use single alkenes [20,25,29], even if they are potentially interfered, due to their higher sensitivity compared to alkadienes. A few studies [18,19] estimated the interference of organic material - simulated by humic acid - to alkenes, reporting it as very low and similar to the limit of quantification. Starting from this point, Okoffo and colleagues [19] chose 1-decene as a quantification marker, assuming that it only derives from PE. They justify the low interference by applying a double-shot pyrolysis, where the first shot (100-300 °C) was used as a clean-up method [19]. Analogously, in this work, a ventilation step was applied to samples before the pyrolysis (200°C, 3 min) to reduce the amount of

interference due to volatile and semi-volatile compounds of the matrix. Thus, both alkanes and alkadienes are considered possible PE identification markers in this work after comparing their abundance in the samples with the OAB.

2-Methyl-1-pentene and 2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene, markers of PP, and tetrafluoroethylene, monomer of PTFE, were detected in humic acid, although they are not known to be produced by pyrolysis of organic material. Analysis by using micro-FTIR confirmed the contamination of commercial humic acid by PTFE and polyolefines, which might include PP (more details in Table SM9), as well as other polymers not detected by Py-GC/MS (PS, PA6, PARA (polyarylamide), etc). Considering this, it is important to highlight that some of the previously identified compounds might not be produced from the pyrolysis of humic acid itself, but from contaminating polymers. This result underlines the importance of having plastic-free certified materials available to carry out this type of test.

Since we cannot discriminate the two contributions to the pyrolytic products and for caution, we calculated the OAB for all the univocal polymer tracers detected before, independently from their origin: alkenes and alkadienes from C₈ to C₁₈, 2,4-dimethyl-1-heptene, and tetrafluoroethylene. The complete set of detected compounds in humic acid is listed in the Supplementary Material (Table SM6).

OAB was calculated considering the typical amount of organic aerosol in TSP, in the period and area of sampling, starting from the pyrolysis of a known amount of humic acid, as reported in the equation:

$$OAB = A_n (\text{counts } \mu\text{g}^{-1}) \cdot OM \cdot PM (\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}) \cdot fl (\text{m}^3\cdot\text{min}^{-1}) \cdot t (\text{min}) \cdot fr_{\text{sample}}$$

where A_n is the average tracer normalised areas in the humic acid pyrograms. OM is the organic matter fraction in the aerosol. In this study, the value used for OM was 30%, above the maximum organic matter content estimated for Venice in a previous study (9-27% [41]). PM is the aerosol concentration. For simulating a typical TSP sample, the choice of PM was based on the air quality information in nearby monitoring stations managed by the Regional Agency for Environmental Prevention and Protection of Veneto (ARPAV) in 19-30 July 2021 and was $29 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ as PM₁₀. For the calculation of PM as total suspended particulate, a ratio PM₁₀/TSP of 0.88 was considered [41]; fl and t are the flow and time of sampling, respectively. A time of 2880

min and 4830 min was set for the 48h- and 72h-samples, respectively, while fr_{sample} represented the fraction of QFF introduced in the sample tube (0.9 %) and was calculated from the area of the disks introduced in the sample tube (20 disks of a diameter of 1.9 mm), compared to the whole sampled area of QFF (diameter 90 mm).

3.3 Polymers in aerosol samples

The application of the Py-GC/MS technique to TSP filters led to the identification of some polymers: PE and PS were detected in S1, and PP was detected in S1 and S3. The presence of PS or other styrene-based polymers in S1 is also confirmed by the Sty/Tol ratio > 1 (3.4). In S2 and S3 pyrograms, alkenes were also identified but their area was lower than the OAB, so we cannot confirm the identification of PE for those samples since alkenes could also derive from organic matter.

The analysis using the Micro-FTIR led to the identification of the same polymers in S1 and S3 (Table 4). This confirmation gave strength to the robustness of the results and demonstrated the applicability of Py-GC/MS for polymer analysis directly in the sampling filter without preparative steps. Micro-FTIR analysis revealed the presence of other polymers in TSP samples, not detected by Py-GC/MS (Tables 3 and SM9). PET was non-identifiable with Micro-FTIR as a single polymer, but particles of polyesters (PES), a class to which PET belongs, were detected in all samples.

The discrepancy between results obtained applying the two techniques are not surprising, indeed, they can provide important information on the characteristics of the two techniques. In a recent paper focusing on the comparison of Py-GC/MS and Micro-FTIR in the analysis of microplastics, Primpke and colleagues [42] evidenced that Micro-FTIR is more selective for functional groups of polyesters and polyamines than Py-GC/MS. That could contribute to the missing identification of PA6, PA12 and PET by using Py-GC/MS observed in this work, together with other factors, such as the small amount of sample inserted and the presence of the matrix. The difficulty in the detection of PET and PA6 could be related to the polarity of the polymer tracers vinyl benzoate and caprolactam. Polar compounds have a low resolution in gas chromatography when using an apolar column and this could reduce the peak height, determine co-elution with other components

and in general complicate the identification. The findings of this work suggest the need for more research on possible alternative tracers for Py-GC/MS, which should be apolar and possibly abundant, to allow the identification of plastic even in low concentrations. For improve PET identification some authors [20,28] suggested conducting the sample pyrolysis in presence of tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) as derivatising agent, leading to the formation of the apolar product 1,4-dimethylterephthalate, more easily detectable.

The crucial point in the experimental approach applied in this work is the portion of the filter practically analysable. Given the very small size of the sample tube, only a small fraction (about 1%) of the sample can be inserted in the pyrolyser chamber and analysed. This has a consequence both in terms of poor representativeness of the polymer profile, and in terms of a low analytical signal: even if the particulate matter were perfectly homogeneously deposited in the filter, the introduction of such a small amount of material could lead to the failure in the identification of some polymers.

The analysis of a larger amount of dust could shed light on the main responsible for the lack of polymer identification in aerosol samples: the low amount of analysed particulate matter, or the presence of the matrix. In the pyrograms of House dust SRM2585 the tracers of PE, PP, PA6, as well as nonanenitrile, a tracer of PA12, were identified (Figure 2). The OAB was recalculated, taking into consideration the real amount of analysed dust and 30% of organic material, as done in the previous sections, and the polymer detection was confirmed (Table 4). The complete set of detected tracers in TSP samples and commercial dust is reported in the Supplementary Material (Tables SM7 and SM8). The analysis carried out by Micro-FTIR confirmed the presence of PE, PP, PA6, and PA12, and revealed the presence of PES, which could be related to PET or other polymers belonging to the class (Table SM9). The remarkable similarity of the results from Py-GC/MS and Micro-FTIR suggests that particulate matter could be analysed, even without a preparatory step, using Py-GC/MS, even if more research is needed for obtaining complete and robust results

4 Conclusions

This work explored the feasibility of a direct analysis of atmospheric aerosol samples via Py-GC/MS. The results obtained on real TSP samples and commercial dust suggest that a direct analysis - without any preparative steps - is possible and could be applied as an explorative technique for obtaining preliminary information about the sample polymer profile. Although the direct analysis was explored on a limited number of samples, the tests carried out were able to highlight both the potential and limits of this possible application.

The direct analysis represents the ideal screening procedure for saving time, costs, and waste; this is even more convenient if considering that plastics are difficult to extract and require dedicated instrumentation. We proposed a simple method assessing the interference due to organic matter, which represents a significant fraction of the total aerosol, by using humic acid as representative of the organic matter. The interference level does not appear to be a major obstacle to polymer detection. The missing polymer identification observed in some samples could be due to practical reasons, specifically, the small quantity of filter analysed. This could create problems of representativeness and the intensity of the analytical signal. This effect can be overcome by increasing the amount of particulate matter inserted in the pyrolyser (i. e., using a larger sample holder or separating the particulate from the filter), as confirmed by the great accordance of the results obtained from the Py-GC/MS analysis of commercial dust with micro-FTIR measurements.

Some difficulties have been experienced in this work for the absence of available material dedicated to the analytical method assessment: the commercial humic acid and dust contain traces of plastics, and this prevents some specific tests. As practical examples: i) the evaluation of the matrix effect was not conducted in this work, since many of the target polymers were already contained in the dust; ii) the calculation of the OAB was made for some polymers which are probably not interfered with by the organic matter, whereas they are present as traces into the material. Another issue revealed from this work is the poor repeatability of the measures, in quantitative terms. This does not have a significant effect on the detection of polymers if multiple tests are carried out per sample, but it is important information to have for a possible quantitative analysis of polymers in aerosols.

Nevertheless, Py-GC/MS has proven to have great potential for the analysis of polymers in aerosol, which can be conducted in a simpler, quicker, and cheaper way than other techniques classically employed for microplastic detection. Further studies are needed to outline a specific approach useful for getting the greatest possible efficiency from the analysis and to answer the question fully “Can we carry out the polymeric characterisation of atmospheric aerosol by using direct inlet Py-GC/MS?”. Depending on the chosen approach (i.e., changing the sampling membranes or developing a simple preparation to separate particulate matter from the filter), Py-GC/MS could be applied only as an exploratory technique or to obtain a qualitative characterization of the sample polymeric profile. Further research is also needed for the selection of the best tracers of plastics: for some polymers (i. e., PVC and PS) the most sensitive indicator peaks can also be produced by other sources and cannot be employed as univocal tracers, thus the choice falls on secondary peaks, which are less easily detectable.

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Table 1. Tested GC programs.

Program	Ramp(s)	Reference
Program A	40°C, 2 min, 13°C min ⁻¹ to 261°C, 6°C min ⁻¹ to 300°C, 2 min	Hermabessiere et al. [25]
Program B	50°C, 2 min, raised at 10°C min ⁻¹ to 320°C, 3 min [26]	Hendrickson et al. [26]
Program C	40°C, 4 min, 5°C min ⁻¹ to 200°C, 10°C min ⁻¹ to 300°C	Funck et al. [27]

Table 2. Tracers of polymers monitored.

PE	Alkanes (C ₈ -C ₁₈)
	Alkenes (C ₈ -C ₁₈) *
	Alkadienes (C ₈ -C ₁₈) *
PET	Benzene
	Acetophenone
	Vinyl benzoate *
	Benzoic acid
	Divinyl terephthalate
PTFE	Tetrafluoroethylene *
PS	Toluene
	Styrene
	Styrene dimer *
	Styrene trimer *
PA6	Caprolactam *
PP	2-Methyl-1-pentene
	2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene *
PVC	Benzene
	Toluene
	Chlorobenzene *
	Styrene
	Indene
	1-Methyl naphthalene
PA12	Alkenes (C ₈ -C ₁₁)
	Alkadienes (C ₈ -C ₁₁)
	Alkanenitriles (C ₈ -C ₁₁)

* Compounds commonly recognised as univocal in the literature

Table 3. The instrumental detection limit (IDL) for polymers markers.

Polymer	Marker	IDL (μg)	Marker	IDL (μg)
PE	1-Octene	0.01	1,7-Octadiene	2
	1-Nonene	0.02	1,8-Nonadiene	0.2
	1-Decene	0.01	1,9-Decadiene	0.5
	1-Undecene	0.01	1,10-Undecadiene	0.2
	1-Dodecene	0.02	1,11-Dodecadiene	0.1
	1-Tridecene	0.05	1,12-Tridecadiene	0.1
	1-Tetradecene	0.01	1,13-Tetradecadiene	0.1
	1-Pentadecene	0.01	1,14-Pentadecadiene	0.01
	1-Hexadecene	0.02	1,15-Hexadecadiene	0.03
	1-Heptadecene	0.01	1,16-Heptadecadiene	0.01
	1-Octadecene	0.02	1,17-Octadecadiene	1
PET	Benzene	0.004	Benzoic acid	0.001
	Acetophenone	0.003	Divinyl terephthalate	0.001
	Vinyl benzoate	0.002		
PTFE	Tetrafluoroethylene	0.0003		
PS	Styrene	0.0005	Styrene dimer	1
PA6	Caprolactam	0.0004		
PP	2-Methyl-1-pentene	0.0002	2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene	0.0002
PVC	Chlorobenzene	4		
PA12	Heptanenitrile	0.01	Decanenitrile	0.02
	Octanenitrile	0.01	Undecanenitrile	0.04
	Nonanenitrile	0.03	Dodecanenitrile	0.04

Table 4. Detected polymers in aerosol samples and dust material (SRM2585) by using Py-GC/MS and Micro-FTIR.

	S1		S2		S3		SRM2585	
	Py-GC/MS	Micro-FTIR	Py-GC/MS	Micro-FTIR	Py-GC/MS	Micro-FTIR	Py-GC/MS	Micro-FTIR
PE	Det	Det (HDPE)		Det (HDPE)		Det (HDPE + LDPE)	Det	Det
PP	Det	Det		Det	Det	Det	Det	Det
PS	Det	Det						
PA6		Det		Det		Det	Det	Det
PA12		Det		Det			Det (nonanenitrile)	Det
PET		(PES)		(PES)		(PES)		(PES)
PTFE				Det		Det		
PVC								

Figure 1. Normalised peak areas for various pyrolysis temperatures.

AP: Acetophenone; VB: Vinyl benzoate; BA: Benzoic acid; DVT: Divinyl terephthalate; CL: Caprolactam.

Figure 2. Pyrogram of SRM2585: total ion current (TIC) and extract of ions m/z 55 from test 1 and m/z 82 from test 3, with identification of polymer indicator compounds.

